

From a failed blood donation attempt to the curing of hepatitis C infection: a case report

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Received 7 January 2026 ♦ Accepted 19 March 2026 ♦ Published 15 April 2026

Citation: Komitova R, Hristamyan M, Kevorkyan A, Atanasova M (2026) From a failed blood donation attempt to the curing of hepatitis C infection: a case report. *Pharmacia* 73: 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e184421>

Abstract

Blood transfusions are essential for effective treatment and high-quality patient care. Screening donated blood for pathogens enables early detection of infections, reduces the risk of disease transmission, and enhances public trust in blood safety. Identifying viruses such as the hepatitis C virus (HCV) facilitates the timely initiation of direct-acting antiviral (DAA) therapy. This report presents a case of a young woman who was diagnosed with HCV infection during routine blood donation screening. Although she was deferred from donating, she began DAA therapy promptly, which resulted in a sustained virological response and complete clearance of the virus. This case demonstrates the value of early detection of infection and curative DAA treatment.

Keywords

Blood transmission, blood donors, hepatitis C virus, nucleic acid amplification technique, direct-acting antivirals

Introduction

Chronic hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection often goes undetected because it usually develops without obvious symptoms for many years. Without treatment, approximately 20–30% of individuals with chronic HCV infection may progress to liver cirrhosis, and up to 5% may develop hepatocellular carcinoma. HCV is discovered incidentally during routine check-ups for issues unrelated to the liver (Alter et al. 1992; Razavi et al. 2020; Polaris Observatory HCV Collaborators 2022). HCV screening is essential for the early detection of HCV infection. Screening typically begins with an HCV antibody test, followed by HCV RNA testing if the antibody test is positive.

The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends a one-time serological test for adults 18 and older, as well

as screening for all pregnant women. High-risk groups, such as intravenous drug users, those living with HIV, and men who have sex with men, should be screened annually (WHO 2022). The primary aim of screening is to identify active infections and connect individuals to effective treatments with direct-acting antivirals (DAA). Modern DAAs are highly effective in treating HCV, achieving sustained virological response (SVR) rates of over 95%. They significantly reduce liver disease progression, hospitalizations, and the risk of cirrhosis and liver cancer (Geddaw et al. 2017). However, challenges in testing, diagnosis, and access to treatment hinder the WHO's goal of eliminating viral hepatitis by 2030 (Musabaev et al. 2025).

Beyond clinical purposes, screening for HCV, along with hepatitis B virus (HBV) and HIV, is routinely performed on blood, blood products, organs, and tissues to

prevent transmission of these pathogens from donor to recipient. This comprehensive screening process is a critical step in protecting recipients from transfusion-transmitted infections (TTIs), including HCV, ensuring greater safety in transfusion and transplantation procedures.

In Bulgaria, hepatitis transmitted through blood transfusions, especially those caused by HBV and HCV, represents a considerable public health concern. Between 2015 and 2017, approximately 12% of hepatitis cases were associated with blood transfusions (Ivanova et al. 2020). Comprehensive testing for TTIs is required for all donated blood to comply with national and EU regulations. Until the end of 2019, blood donations were screened for HIV-1, HIV-2, HBV, and HCV. The introduction of Nucleic Acid Testing (NAT) in 2020 has enhanced safety by enabling earlier detection of infection than traditional testing methods (Roth 2019).

The report details the case of a young woman who does not fall into a high-risk category for TTIs, diagnosed with HCV infection during routine blood donation screening. Following her diagnosis, she swiftly initiated treatment with DAAs and ultimately achieved a complete cure. The findings emphasize the need for thorough screening of all donated blood to prevent transfusion-transmitted TTIs. Furthermore, they highlight the role of DAAs in effectively eradicating HCV infections.

Case presentation

A 32-year-old woman donated blood for the first time in March 2023. In April, the Blood Transfusion Centre in Plovdiv informed her that her blood tested positive for HCV and advised her to consult a physician for further evaluation. Repeat serological testing confirmed HCV infection. An epidemiological investigation conducted by the regional health inspectorate found that her husband and son tested negative for HCV. In May, an infectious disease specialist found no symptoms or physical abnormalities. Her medical history includes a laparoscopic cholecystectomy in 2017 and Hashimoto's thyroiditis, managed with thyroxine therapy. She also reported having a piercing performed in the hospital at age 14, which was later removed.

Laboratory studies were unremarkable except for mildly elevated aminotransferase levels (Table 1). Serological testing confirmed the presence of anti-HCV antibodies. HCV RNA was detected by PCR (Bioneer, South Korea) at a level of 240,000 IU/mL, confirming active HCV infection. Serological markers for hepatitis A virus and HBV were negative. Her liver stiffness was not measured, and FIB-4, a non-invasive marker of liver fibrosis, was calculated at 0.92. She was enrolled in the HCV treatment program and received a two-month course of oral pangenotypic DAA, specifically glecaprevir/pibrentasvir. At the end of treatment, HCV RNA was undetectable, and it remained so six months later, confirming an SVR and cure. Unfortunately, the patient was lost to follow-up.

Table 1. Laboratory investigations on admission.

Variable	On admission	Reference range
Hemoglobin, g/l	132	120–150
WBC x10 ⁹ /l	7.5	3.5–10.5
Tc x10 ⁹ /l	214	150–350
INR	1.07	< 1.2
Bilirubin, μmol/l	12	5–21
ALT, U/l	62	< 35
AST, U/l	65	< 34
Protein, g/l	81	60–82
Albumin, g/l	40	33–52
Glucose, mmol/l	5.8	3.4–6.1
HBsAg	nonreactive	nonreactive
HAV IgM	nonreactive	nonreactive
HCV Ab	reactive	nonreactive
HCV RNA	240 000 IU/mL	undetectable
FIB-4 *	0.93	< 1.3 exclusion of fibrosis
Abdominal sonography	Liver steatosis	

Abbreviations: WBC – white blood cells, Tc – thrombocytes, INR – international normalized ratio, AST – aspartate aminotransferase, ALT – alanine aminotransferase, HBsAg – surface antigen, HAV IgM – antibody to hepatitis A virus, HCV Ab – antibody to hepatitis C virus, FIB-4 – non-invasive marker of fibrosis (Catanzaro et al. 2021).

*FIB-4 score was by: (age [years] × AST [U/L]) / (platelet count [10⁹/L] × (ALT [U/L]^{1/2}) using laboratory values.

Discussion

This case illustrates the importance of rigorous screening of donated blood to prevent TTIs, especially HCV. Interestingly, it was during the donor screening process that HCV was identified in the patient, allowing for prompt diagnosis and effective treatment.

How to identify a potential blood donor

Blood transfusion is a vital medical intervention that can be life-saving in a wide range of situations, including surgical procedures, traumatic injuries, accidents, blood disorders, and complications arising from cancer or kidney diseases (Ainley and Hewitt 2018). In developed countries, numerous measures ensure the safety of blood transfusions, such as thorough donor selection, rigorous laboratory screening, bacterial culturing of blood components like platelets, and the pathogen reduction technique.

Prevention of TTIs is essential for blood transfusion safety. Some donors may be asymptomatic during infection, and certain pathogens can persist throughout blood processing and storage, such as bacteria in platelet concentrates or prions (Bryant and Klein 2007).

Selection of blood donors

Selection of blood donors is the critical first step for ensuring blood safety. This process includes a questionnaire designed to gather information about the donor's medical history and potential risk factors for TTIs. Permanent exclusions apply to those with HIV, HBV, HCV, syphilis,

high-risk behaviors, prison inmates, and individuals with certain cosmetic procedures (WHO 2012). There may have been a potential lapse in proper endoscopic reprocessing and sterilization in our patient.

There are three global models for providing blood to patients: voluntary, non-remunerative donors, paid donors, and family or replacement donors (WHO 2012). Voluntary, non-remunerative blood donors are considered the optimal source for ensuring an adequate and reliable blood supply (WHO 2025).

Testing donated blood for TTIs

Classically tested transfusion transmitted infections include *Treponema pallidum*, HIV, HCV and HBV. In recent years, some regions have implemented pathogen screening during local outbreaks or periods of ongoing vector-borne transmission (Busch et al. 2019; Denner et al. 2019). Blood testing for these three viruses includes both serological assays and NAT for the sensitive and rapid detection of viral genetic material. The primary advantage of NAT is that it enhances blood transfusion safety by detecting infections early during the „window period.“ In this phase, antibodies are not yet detectable, but the blood can still transmit infections, posing a risk to recipients. For instance, antibodies to HCV can be detected 1 to 3 months after infection, while HCV RNA can be identified much earlier, within 5 to 8 days post-infection (Lauer and Walker 2001). In the case of HIV infection, NAT can shorten this detection period to just 10 to 15 days (Le Corfec et al. 1999; Zou et al. 2010). Furthermore, NAT correlates more accurately with current infection activity compared to serological assays, which only indicate past exposure, except in the case of HIV (Bloch 2022). NAT is also capable of identifying occult infections and mutant viruses that may not be detected by traditional diagnostic methods (Roth 2019). Furthermore, direct detection of viral DNA or RNA reduces the likelihood of false-negative results during early stages of infection. Nevertheless, the higher costs and technical requirements associated with NAT limit its availability primarily to high-income countries.

In developed countries, blood screening typically involves an initial test, followed by a repeat test if the result is positive, and then a confirmatory test using a different method. These steps are based on the prevalence and incidence of viral infections in the population. Simultaneous serological testing and NAT are used to identify and classify donors infected with HCV. This classification includes categories such as acute (HCV RNA-positive and antibody-negative), presumptively resolved (HCV RNA-negative and antibody-positive), and active (HCV RNA-positive and antibody-positive), as demonstrated in this case.

Positive blood samples are discarded, and the donor is permanently deferred from donation (Selvarajah and Busch 2012).

Blood transfusion centers notify individuals who have been infected and advise them to seek medical attention, as in the case presented. They also inform the regional health inspectorate to ensure ongoing surveillance.

Screening for TTIs has significantly enhanced the safety and reliability of blood transfusion. The risk of post-transfusion HBV and HCV infections has been reduced to negligible levels, specifically 1 in 1.5 million blood donations for HBV and 1 in 2.6 million blood donations for HCV (Abdallah et al. 2021). Nevertheless, the risk of TTIs cannot be fully eliminated. In the first 8 to 10 days of acute HCV infection, HCV RNA levels increase rapidly, resulting in high infectivity, while antibodies remain undetectable. Ultrasensitive RNA testing plays a critical role in facilitating early diagnosis (Glynn et al. 2005). Following the implementation of NAT in Germany in 1999, only two cases of post-transfusion HCV transmission have been reported (Kretzschmar et al. 2007; Himmelsbach et al. 2023). Furthermore, implementing pathogen inactivation techniques in platelet and plasma products enhances safety (Bryant and Klein 2007; Zeng et al. 2020).

How to treat a newly diagnosed HCV infection

Early identification of HCV-infected patients allows for prompt administration of DAAs. DAAs have transformed HCV treatment into first-line therapy and are key to global elimination efforts (Zeng et al. 2020). Introduced between 2013 and 2014, they replaced older interferon-based therapies that were longer, more toxic, and less effective. Following the removal of prescribing restrictions in 2018, DAAs became widely accessible. However, uninsured populations, including some people who inject drugs, still encounter challenges (Flisiak et al. 2022). In Bulgaria, DAAs have been fully covered by the National Health Insurance Fund for insured individuals, resulting in significantly improved access.

Advantages of DAAs include a shorter treatment duration of 8 to 12 weeks and fewer side effects. These medications are effective even for difficult-to-treat populations, such as individuals with HIV co-infection, cirrhosis, those who have undergone liver transplants, and patients who have experienced relapses. Recent pangenotypic formulations have removed the necessity for genotypic testing, making treatment more accessible worldwide. Examples of these medications include sofosbuvir/velpatasvir and glecaprevir/pibrentasvir, the latter of which was used for the patient discussed (Di Marco et al. 2025). The principal advantage of DAAs is their ability to achieve an SVR in approximately 95% of cases, thereby curing HCV infections. This outcome results in viral clearance, minimizes liver damage, supports liver tissue repair, and improves insulin sensitivity. The reversal of fibrosis can be assessed through liver stiffness measurements or non-invasive markers such as the FIB-4 index and the AST-to-Platelet Ratio Index (APRI) (Catanzaro et al. 2021). Unfortunately, our patient did not return for follow-up, which is a limitation of the study. However, her FIB-4 score indicated no detectable liver fibrosis, emphasizing the importance of early HCV diagnosis and DAA treatment in preventing complications.

Conclusion

The patient presented was diagnosed with HCV infection during a blood donation attempt. Although she was ultimately deferred from donating blood, she promptly received targeted, curative DAA therapy. This case reinforces the importance of early detection of infection and the benefit of initiating prompt treatment with DAAs.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent was obtained from the patient, and their anonymity has been preserved throughout. Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Medical University Plovdiv.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

R.K.: conceptualization of the study, patient management, manuscript drafting, and critical revisions; M.H.: literature review, data collection; partial preparation of introduction and discussion sections; and manuscript editing; A.K.: diagnostic data analysis, clinical evaluation, and correlation with transfusion safety; and critical revisions; M.A.: pharmacological review and contribution to manuscript editing. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All the data underpinning the results of this study are included within the primary content of the document.

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